

COMPOSITE GRID/FRAME STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

We have discovered that grid structures made of interlaced unidirectional composites can combine the superior properties of composite materials with low cost manufacturing. Although this is a new form of composite structures, it follows the path of classical laminated plate theory wherein analogous models for the predictions of stiffness and strength of unfilled and filled grid/frame have been developed and validated experimentally. While the manufacturing methodologies are gradually emerging, many applications seem highly cost effective and can lead to significant and extensive use of composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

In order to secure funding from industry, we have found it necessary to follow a problem-solving path. Timely, definitive solutions are more valuable than sophisticated formulation. Emphasis is invariably placed on cost, reliability and maintainability. In fact, one editorial and one article appeared in a February 1995 issues of *Aviation Week and Space Technology* citing the frustration of commercial airlines in the maintenance of composite structures. Southwest Airline had planned to replace its B-737 composite engine cowl with an aluminum design because of the frequency and cost of repair. It is our realization that our research effort must address many mundane issues with the same sense of urgency as research in failure mechanisms.

In this presentation, we will describe an on-going research program which is focused on a generic product form - composite grid/frame structures. Working with our industrial partners and sponsors we hope to bring to the market place cost-effective products and processes in 3 years. While we all are familiar with the outstanding properties of composite materials, we are trying to promote their low cost opportunities. Many new forms of finished structures can emerge from this basic generic grid form.

BACKGROUND

Composite structures can be made by many processes. The most common ones for high-performance structures include pultrusion, filament winding, RTM, fiber placement and other layup processes. In all these processes, unidirectional fibers are placed at various angles to achieve a balanced stiffness and strength in more than one direction. When multidirectional structures are built, initial failures can be either micro cracking within a ply or delamination between plies.

These premature failure modes often prevent a full realization of the fiber strength. A popular design philosophy among many companies is to limit the failure strain of a laminated composite to less than 0.4 percent as determined by the threshold of micro cracking. Delamination failure impose further limit on design. Such conservative philosophy has often prevented composite materials to be competitive. Light weight and corrosion and fatigue resistances and other unique manufacturing opportunities are often not affordable.

A grid structure can make composites more competitive than the classical laminated structure. In civil engineering, grid and lattice structures have been in use for years. The famous WWII English bomber, Wellington, was built with a metallic grid or geodesic structures and its damage tolerance was well documented. Composite isogrid structures were studied by McDonnell Douglas and Larry Rehfield in the late 1970's, and later by Lockheed Aircraft in the 1980's. Extensive usage did not materialize because of the lack of design methodology and the high cost of manufacturing. Square grid structures were made by a Japanese consortium for reinforcing concrete. A patent was issued in 1987. Various composite grid structures made in the USSR were also shown in V. Vesiliev's book in 1988.

With encouragement from Jim Koury of the USAF Phillips Laboratory in the early 1990's, we began to explore the potentials of composite grid structures. Our initial efforts have been to develop design methodology, low cost manufacturing and test data. These are generic issues and, if successful, can lead to many applications.

MANUFACTURING

In manufacturing of grid structures, we have explored several methods. The objectives are straightforward:

- All ribs must be unidirectional
- Rib cross section must be well defined and remains constant
- Nodes are interlaced with continuous composite layers

The selection of a particular manufacturing process is often dictated by the tooling and the volume fraction of fibers desired. For example, the volume fraction of fibers in the rib can be dictated by that of the interlaced nodes. If it is lower than 30 percent, interlaced nodes can be built without difficulty assuming that the volume fraction at the nodes would be twice that of the rib or 60 percent. This is the upper limit of fiber volume fractions in most available composite grating and "geogrid" systems having orthogonal grids.

If a higher fiber fraction in the rib is desired, special designs of the intersecting layers at the nodes must be made. One such design developed by USAF Phillips Laboratory is to offset the nodes; i.e., one triple-layered nodes in an isogrid can be spread over three double-layered nodes. The grid will have two triangles of difference sizes. The smaller triangle can be the offset triple node.

Another design that we have developed at Stanford is to have wider nodes that would reduce the thickness of interlacing layers. In the limit, the fiber volume fraction of the nodes will be the same as that of the ribs. For double-layered nodes, the width would be twice that of the rib; for triple-layered nodes, three time the rib. There are other tooling concepts that would be amenable to low cost manufacturing. Based on our findings, we prefer the use of hard rather than soft tooling. Filament winding and a vacuum infiltration process "SCRIMP" offer additional cost savings while maintaining superior structural performances.

UNIQUE FEATURES

Several features of grid structures were expected and found to be true based on our data thus far:

- Having a homogeneous instead of a laminated rib, delamination failure can be suppressed. Nodes have not failed prematurely in our tests.
- Grid constructions have built-in redundant load paths. The structures are intrinsically damage tolerant.
- Grid constructions are open and modular which can simplify inspection, joining and repair.

Other features of grid structures were not obvious to us when we started three years ago:

- Unidirectional composite materials are unique for forming the ribs of grid structures. Because of anisotropy the high translation of the longitudinal properties to the grid properties cannot be matched by isotropic materials of the same grid geometry.
- Graphite grid structures have zero thermal and moisture expansions in two dimensions; i.e., in the plane of the grid. This is different from zero expansion from laminates which can only be achieved in one direction. When zero expansion is achieved in two directions it is zero in all directions. This unique property may be utilized in building dimensionally stable plane-like structures which can eliminate the need of expansion joints. Or in the case of precision machines where temperature and humidity controls are required to limit dimensional variability, graphite grid/frame structures can be cost competitive against metallic designs.
- Low cost manufacturing is already available. The cost for glass fiber/polyester grid is US\$3 per pound, with dimensions of 12' x 4' and thickness up to 1-1/2" thick. The fiber volume fraction is 20 percent. Similar grid of graphite/vinylester grid is being made at an anticipated cost of \$6 per pound. Other processes are being explored and can yield products with higher performance at a higher cost. It is our intent to keep the cost as low as possible so we can compete against conventional steel structures. With automation in manufacturing, we have identified a number of potential applications.

ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION

Analysis of grid structures has been completed by two recent PhD theses at Stanford University. Hong-Ji Chen used an effective stiffness model that performs a point-stress analysis of a grid having rib oriented in 0, 90 and +/- angles with an upper and/or lower or no skin. The analysis is analogous to classical laminated plate theory that defines the grid stiffnesses by A, B, D matrices. We can have square grid, orthogrid, angle-grid, isogrid, Pi/3 or Pi/4 grid, and so on. A rigid-body rotation can also be included. Like laminated plate theory, applied in-plane stress {N} and bending moment {M} are user-defined. This spreadsheet-based program Mic-Mac/Grid yields stiffness and compliance components. It also identifies the strength ratio at the initial failure and its particular mode. Failure modes include rib strength, rib buckling, skin ply-by-ply strength and skin buckling. A built-in optimizer selects in minutes on a fast PC a grid design subjected up to five multiple loading conditions.

We can then use a two-step structural optimization. First we use Mic-Mac/Grid to select an optimum grid at highly stressed points within a structure. The resulting effective stiffness of the grid is used for a finite element analysis of the structure. From a new set of internal loads at critical locations, Mic-Mac/Grid is used again to have a new grid design. Another finite element analysis is performed. This iterative process is repeated until a good design is reached. The effective stiffness approach is particularly suited for structural optimization because the

grid design is uncoupled from the finite element analysis. Remeshing is not necessary as we try a different grid design.

Steve Huybrechts developed a finite element analysis of the grid that takes into account of the local rib and nodal designs, including the offset nodes useful for isogrid structures. His model is particularly powerful to assess the effects of defect/damage that may be present in a grid structure. The removal of a rib or node is easily accomplished and shows the resulting load redistribution. Damage tolerance of a grid can be quantitatively assessed. The same model can predict the deformation and strength of the grid in the presence of openings, reinforcements or a repair. Also important for grid structures are the methods of termination and joining. Steve Huybrechts' model is easy to use to address these local design issues.

FILLER MATERIALS

Frames are built with layers of grid positioned by columns/struts bonded through the grid openings. Frames can then be filled with another material to provide lateral support of ribs. Such support would increase the buckling resistance of the ribs which would increase the load-carrying capability of the grid when rib buckling is the limiting failure mode. The filler material provides another important function. It increases the in-plane shear rigidity of an orthogrid. While isogrid has excellent shear rigidity it is more difficult to manufacture due to the additional rib direction and the triple-layered nodes. A good alternative is to use orthogrid. We can then rely on the filler material to increase the shear rigidity of the orthogrid.

Most attractive filler material for grid/frame structures can be either foam or concrete. As we have stated that the filler material would enhance the properties of grid/frame structures. The grid/frame structures in turn will reinforce the filler material. It is possible to select an optimum combination of materials of a filled orthogrid structure.

Frames made from grid structures can be in many configurations. One common configuration would be a sandwich construction where two sheets of orthogrid are the facing material. Another configuration would be unsymmetric with only one layer of grid located on the tensile side of a concrete slab, for example. For resistance to twisting moment a layer of grid may be located in the mid-plane of a concrete slab. Thus multiple layers can be easily configured to provide the best combination of resistance to bending and twisting moments.

The models for such symmetric and unsymmetric configurations would follow those well established models of laminated constructions commonly used for composite structures. On the layer level, a contact model between a grid and filler material can predict the effective stiffness of a filled grid layer. Depending on the positions of the filled grid layers, the A, B, D matrices of the filled frame configuration can be easily derived. Thus structural optimization of a filled frame such as a grid-reinforced concrete structure can be done in the same 2 steps for unfilled grid outlined earlier.

The first step is the filled grid layer using a modified Mic-Mac/Grid. A contact model between the filler and the grid is assumed, from which the stiffness of the filled grid layer is predicted. Then the stiffness of a laminated structure having layers of filled grid and solid filler material can be calculated as a part of Mic-Mac/Grid. The structural analysis using finite element method will be the second step like the optimization process cited earlier. The two steps can be repeated until a structure is optimized.

TESTING

Extensive testing of grid structures with and without filler have been underway. While analysis can predict stress, strain and deformation, failure mechanisms must be observed by tests. A variety of tests have been performed to subject grid/frame to different failure mechanisms. The tests include the following:

- Ribs and Nodes: Tensile stiffness and strength
- Unfilled Grid: Tensile tests
Three-point bend tests
Three-point twisting tests
- Filled Grid: Same as those for unfilled grid
- Unfilled Frame: Same tests
- Filled Frame: Same tests

The objectives of these tests are many. First, we wish to establish from the simple rib and node tests as inputs to Mic-Mac/Grid which can then predict the stiffness and strength of grid structures. Simple grid structures under various loading conditions will be tested to validate our models. Then grid with filler is tested to validate our contact model. Strength and failure modes can then be assessed.

Frames can be made from layer(s) of grid and the degree of shear transfer can be evaluated. If classical laminated plate theory is proven for filled frame, design and optimization can be achieved with the same degree of success as any laminated structure. Analogous strength and failure modes can be established.

APPLICATIONS

Grid/frame structures with or without filler and skins are generic configurations that can be applied for a variety of applications. Grid/frame without filler can be used to replace stiffened structures. Such structures can be flat, curved or cylindrical. The success of such application will depend invariably on the superior structural performance and low cost. With automation grid structures can compete effectively. The advantages in performance include the suppression of the delamination, and built-in redundancy. Corrosion and fatigue resistances of composite materials can be claimed for grid structures similar to those of laminated structures. Other advantages of grid structures include easy inspection, repair, and joining because these structures are open and modular.

Frame structures consisting multiple grid layers can be assembled by bonding struts to the grid openings in a straightforward manner. The shear transfer among the grid layers depend on the degree of fixity. One method would be the use of a filler material having sufficient shear stiffness to form a sandwich configuration. Concrete or foam can be excellent filler material because of the low material and fabrication costs. These filler materials reinforce the grid/frame structures, and vice versa. Such a composite configuration and resulting structure are fundamentally different from the conventional sandwich panels and steel reinforced concrete structures.

CONCLUSIONS

We believe that grid/frame structures can be an alternative to the conventional composite structures made of lamination. Cost effective manufacturing process and easy design methodology can help in leading to many applications. We have found that the design of laminated structures and composite materials in general can be easily extended to grid/frame structures. Competitive cost would most likely determine the number and size of the applications. We are optimistic and look forward to working with other individuals and organizations to promote these structures.

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